

Selection process of the tools evaluated in the experiment described in the paper

“Automated Data Extraction in Software Engineering SLRs: Promise, Pitfalls, and the Role of Human Oversight”

This document briefly outlines the steps followed to select the tools that will be evaluated in terms of their performance in conducting data extraction tasks within the context of Systematic Literature Reviews (SLRs).

First, a review of the existing literature was conducted, focusing on the use of AI-based tools for automating tasks related to SLRs.

Second, from the results of this review, a set of tools mentioned either as currently used or as potentially suitable for SLRs-related tasks was extracted. Additionally, an internet-based search was conducted focusing exclusively on tools for PDF extraction. This complementary search aimed to identify specialized software and platforms designed to facilitate the automated extraction of information directly from PDF documents, which is a critical step in the data extraction phase of Systematic Literature Reviews.

Third, the identified tools were analyzed based on their characteristics and suitability for the project's objectives. As a result of this analysis, three tools were selected for evaluation: ChatGPT, ChatPDF, and Google NotebookLM.

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1. Literature Search Process and analyzed papers

A review of the existing literature was conducted, focusing on the use of AI-based tools for automating tasks related to Systematic Literature Reviews (SLRs).

The initial searches were exploratory in nature and were carried out using platforms such as Google Scholar and Consensus, with the aim of gaining a general overview of the research landscape in this area.

Subsequently, once a clearer picture of the field had been formed, a more systematic search was conducted using Scopus, in order to retrieve relevant peer-reviewed publications and ensure broader coverage of academic sources.

1.2 Articles Identified Through Google Scholar Search

- [MSR187 Automated Data Extraction in Systematic Literature Reviews \(SLRs\): Assessing the Accuracy and Reliability of a Large Language Model \(LLM\)](#)
- [MSR29 Automated Data Extraction Using Artificial Intelligence to Accelerate Systematic Literature Reviews in Rheumatoid Arthritis](#)
- [MSR5 Accuracy of Automated Data Extraction for Systematic Literature Reviews](#)
- [Collaborative Large Language Models for Automated Data Extraction in Living Systematic Reviews](#)
- [The PDF Data Extractor \(PDE\) Pre-screening Tool Reduced the Manual Review Burden for Systematic Literature Reviews by Over 35% Through Automated High-Throughput Assessment of Full-Text Articles](#)
- [MSR35 Is GPT-4o Capable of Automating Detailed Data Extraction for Systematic Literature Reviews \(SLRs\)?](#)
- [Automated and Semi-Automated Approaches for Literature Searching, Screening, and Data Extraction for Systematic Reviews in Environmental Health](#)
- [Evaluation of a prototype machine learning tool to semi-automate data extraction for systematic literature reviews](#)
- [The emergence of Large Language Models \(LLM\) as a tool in literature reviews: an LLM automated systematic review](#)
- [A survey on current use of software tools for systematic literature reviews](#)

- [Accuracy and reliability of data extraction for systematic reviews using large language models: A protocol for a prospective study](#)
- [Automating Systematic Literature Reviews with Retrieval-Augmented Generation: A Comprehensive Overview](#)
- [A Hybrid Semi-Automated Workflow for Systematic and Literature Review Processes with Large Language Model Analysis](#)
- [Automating Systematic Literature Reviews with Natural Language Processing and Text Mining: a Systematic Literature Review](#)
- [Transformative Automation: AI in Scientific Literature Reviews](#)
- [Automated Mass Extraction of Over 680,000 PICOs from Clinical Study Abstracts Using Generative AI: A Proof-of-Concept Study](#)
- [Large language models streamline automated systematic review: A preliminary study](#)
- [Twister: A Tool for Reducing Screening Time in Systematic Literature Reviews](#)
- [Can large language models replace humans in the systematic review process? Evaluating GPT-4's efficacy in screening and extracting data from peer-reviewed and grey literature in multiple languages](#)
- [Efficient Automated Processing of the Unstructured Documents Using Artificial Intelligence: A Systematic Literature Review and Future Directions](#)
- [Scaling Systematic Literature Reviews with Machine Learning Pipelines](#)
- [Automated Mass Extraction of Over 680,000 PICOs from Clinical Study Abstracts Using Generative AI: A Proof-of-Concept Study](#)

1.3 Articles Identified Through Consensus Search

- [Methods for using Bing's AI-powered search engine for data extraction for a systematic review \(*Research Synthesis Methods*\)](#)
- [Data extraction methods for systematic review \(semi\)automation: Update of a living systematic review](#)
- [PDF text classification to leverage information extraction from publication reports](#)
- [\(Semi\)automated approaches to data extraction for systematic reviews and meta-analyses in social sciences: A living review](#)
- [Software tools for systematic review literature screening and data extraction: Qualitative user experiences from succinct formal tests.](#)

- [Fully Automated Scholarly Search for Biomedical Systematic Literature Reviews](#)
- [Automating Systematic Literature Reviews with Retrieval-Augmented Generation: A Comprehensive Overview](#)
- [A Hybrid Semi-Automated Workflow for Systematic and Literature Review Processes with Large Language Model Analysis](#)
- [Transformative Automation: AI in Scientific Literature Reviews](#)
- [Collaborative Large Language Models for Automated Data Extraction in Living Systematic Reviews](#)
- [Accuracy and reliability of data extraction for systematic reviews using large language models: A protocol for a prospective study](#)
- [The emergence of Large Language Models \(LLM\) as a tool in literature reviews: an LLM automated systematic review](#)
- [AID-SLR: A Generative Artificial Intelligence-Driven Automated System for Systematic Literature Review](#)
- [Exploring the use of a Large Language Model for data extraction in systematic reviews: a rapid feasibility study](#)
- [System for systematic literature review using multiple AI agents: Concept and an empirical evaluation](#)
- [Inter-reviewer reliability of human literature reviewing and implications for the introduction of machine-assisted systematic reviews: a mixed-methods review](#)

1.4 Articles Identified Through Scopus Search

The following keywords were used in various combinations during the Scopus search in order to retrieve literature related to the application of AI tools in Systematic Literature Reviews (SLRs), particularly those supporting document processing and data extraction tasks:

- **AI-related terms:**

Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, AI, Deep Learning, ChatBot

- **SLR-related term:**

Review

- **Document processing and data extraction terms:**

PDF Reader, Document Analysis, Information Extraction, Document Processing, Literature Mining

These terms were combined using Boolean operators to form targeted search strings.

```
("Artificial Intelligence" OR "Machine Learning" OR AI OR "Deep Learning" OR "ChatBot")  
  
AND  
  
("Systematic Literature Review*" OR "SLR*")  
  
AND  
  
("PDF Read*" OR "Document Analy*" OR "Information Extract*" OR "Data Extract*" OR "Document Process*" OR "Literature Min*")
```

The search aimed to capture articles that discuss or evaluate tools capable of processing academic documents (mainly, analysis and extraction) and supporting automated or semi-automated steps within the SLR workflow.

Among the identified studies we cited:

- [Implementation and evaluation of an additional GPT-4-based reviewer in PRISMA-based medical systematic literature reviews](#)
- [Evaluation of a prototype machine learning tool to semi-automate data extraction for systematic literature reviews](#)
- [Natural language processing was effective in assisting rapid title and abstract screening when updating systematic reviews](#)
- [Artificial intelligence in systematic literature reviews - a case for cautious optimism](#)
- [Convolutional neural network for core sections identification in scientific research publications](#)
- [Methods for using Bing's AI-powered search engine for data extraction for a systematic review](#)
- [Data extraction methods for systematic review \(semi\)automation - Update of a living systematic review](#)
- [PDF text classification to leverage information extraction from publication reports](#)
- [\(Semi\)automated approaches to data extraction for systematic reviews and meta-analyses in social sciences - A living review](#)

2. Tools and selection of tools

This section presents the tools identified not only from the literature reviewed in the previously retrieved articles, but also from an additional web-based search conducted with a specific focus on tools for PDF extraction. This broader approach allowed us to consider both academically recognized and publicly available tools relevant to automated data extraction from research papers.

Furthermore, the possibility of using locally installed tools was also considered. However, this option was quickly ruled out due to limitations related to accessibility, scalability, and ease of installation.

2.1. List of Tools Identified in Scientific Articles

Based on the literature review, a number of tools were identified as being used or proposed for automating tasks in the context of Systematic Literature Reviews (SLRs). These tools are presented below, grouped according to key criteria.

Large Language Models (LLMs)

- **GPT-4 / GPT-4o** – OpenAI’s LLM, used for structured data extraction into formats such as JSON.
- **Claude-3** – LLM developed by Anthropic.
- **Mixtral 8x7B** – A mixture-of-experts model developed by Mistral AI.
- **LLaMA** – Meta’s family of open-source LLMs.
- **Gemini 1.5 Pro** – Google’s advanced LLM with multimodal capabilities.
- **Other domain-specific LLMs** – Including *SciBERT*, *ChemGPT*, and other models tailored to scientific literature.

Systematic Literature Review (SLR) Tools

- **ASReview** – Uses active learning to support SLR screening.
- **Abstrackr** – Interactive tool using reviewer feedback for document classification (widely used in health sciences).
- **EPPI-Reviewer** – Tool used mainly in medical domains for managing SLR workflows.
- **FAST / FASTREAD / FAST2** – Tools offering various strategies for identifying relevant documents.
- **Covidence** – Workflow management tool for SLRs (not LLM-based).
- **DistillerSR** – Comprehensive review management system.
- **Rayyan** – Web-based tool for literature screening.
- **SRDR+**, **SYRF** – SLR workflow tools not based on LLMs.
- **RobotReviewer / RobotSearch** – Focused on automating risk of bias assessment in clinical trials.

Clustering and Conceptual Analysis Tools

- **Lingo3G** – Document clustering algorithm to group similar research papers.
- **TheoryOn** – Ontology-based search engine designed for academic researchers.

Qualitative Analysis Tools

- **ATLAS.ti** – Software for qualitative data analysis with ML/NLP features.
- **NVivo** – Qualitative analysis software with machine learning and NLP capabilities.

Data Extraction Tools

- **WebPlotDigitizer** – Extracts numerical data from statistical charts.
- **Graph2Data** – Extracts data points from scientific graphs.

Chatbots and PDF Assistants

- **ChatGPT / CGT** – Used to develop preliminary search strategies through prompt-based interaction.
- **ChatPDF** – Allows users to ask direct questions to PDF documents.

Search and Methodology Tools

- **Litbaskets** – Supports search methodology design by estimating responses.
- **LitSonar** – Automates search translation across multiple indexing systems.

NLP Models and Libraries

- **BioBERT-Base** – BERT-based model pre-trained on biomedical text.
- **fastText** – Library for word embeddings and text classification.
- **Gensim** – Library for topic modeling and vector space modeling.
- **spaCy** – Advanced NLP library with robust pre-trained models.
- **Word2Vec** – Technique for generating word embeddings from large corpora.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Systems

- **RAG / Re2G / SELF-RAG** – Includes variants such as T5, BART, EPR, RETRO, UDR, ITER-RETGEN, REPLUG, In-Context RALM, FLARE, IRCot, among others.

Tools with Insufficient Information

These tools were mentioned in various sources but lacked sufficient documentation or technical detail for further evaluation: Colandr, LitSuggest, Giotto Compliance, Nested Knowledge, PICOPortal, Pitts.ai, Research Screener,

SWIFT-Active Screener, SWIFT-Review, SysRev, Dextr, ExaCT, Iris.ai, Linked Data, PEx / Revis, Review Toolkit, SluRp, SLRONT, SLR-Tool, StArt, UNITEX, RobotAnalyst

2.2. List of tools for PDF extraction

Tool	Functionality	Free Features	Monthly Price
Iris.ai Extraction Tool	-		
AnythingLLM	Local Tool (unspecified)	-	-
GPT4All	Local Tool (unspecified)	-	-
LM Studio	Local Tool (unspecified)	-	-
Chatize	Chat with PDF	2 documents & 20 questions/day	\$15
ChatPDF	Chat with PDF	2 documents/day	\$8.99
Knowledgeie	Chat with PDF	50 questions/month	\$7.50
MyAskAI	Chat with PDF	30 days usage	\$60
PDF.ai	Chat with PDF	100 questions/month	\$10
Wondershare HiPDF	Chat with PDF	5,000 tokens	\$5.99
Chatbase	Chat with PDF (Chatbot)	100 questions/month	\$40
ChatGPT	Chat with PDF (Chatbot)	-	-
Wondershare PDFelement	Chat with PDF (PDF editor)	25 documents	\$49
TextCortex	Chat with PDF (workflow-based)	100 + 20 "analyses" per day	\$5.59
Humata	Chat with PDF (research manager)	60 pages/month	\$1.99-\$9.99
SciSpace	Chat with PDF (research manager)	Limit unclear	-
Algolia	Chat with PDF (search engine)	10,000 searches/month	\$0.50 per 1,000 searches
AlgoDocs	Automatic PDF Data Extraction	50 pages/month	\$23
Docsumo	Automatic PDF Data Extraction	100 pages	\$299
Mindee	Automatic PDF Data Extraction	25 pages	\$0.10 per page
Parseur	Automatic PDF Data Extraction	20 pages/month	\$39
Parsio	Automatic PDF Data Extraction	30 documents	\$41

Link.ai Article Summarizer	Article Summarizer	Limit unclear	\$7.40
Musley.ai Article Summarizer	Article Summarizer	Limit unclear	–

2.3. Own implementation

While there are indeed local LLMs available, they are not oriented toward science-specific applications—let alone toward **automated data extraction** or **chatbot-style interfaces** tailored to scientific or technological contexts. This highlights a current gap in the ecosystem of research tools and may inform future tool development or selection strategies.

Resources:

- [Installing and using ollama](#)
- [Using ChatPDF with Ollama](#)
- [RagFlow](#)
- [Scientific LLMs](#)

Comparison of Local LLM Deployment Tools

Feature	Ollama	TGI (Text Generation Inference)	LM Studio	FastChat
Ease of Use	Very easy (simple CLI and API)	Moderate (requires advanced setup)	Very easy (GUI and CLI)	Moderate (requires advanced setup)
Multi-user Support	Limited, intended for local use	Excellent, designed for server deployment	Local only (not designed for multi-user)	Good, supports multiple clients
Server Performance	Good, but less optimized for scalable serving	Highly optimized for GPU-based server environments	Not designed for server use	Optimized for server performance
Model Compatibility	LLaMA, Mistral, Gemma, and other GGUF models	LLaMA, Falcon, Mistral, BLOOM, OPT (via HuggingFace Transformers)	GGUF models	LLaMA, Vicuna, OpenAI API, other LLMs
GPU Support	Yes, but less efficient than TGI	Excellent, optimized with TensorRT and vLLM	Yes (via GGUF, less optimized for scaling)	Yes, with vLLM support

PDF Integration	Requires external libraries (e.g., PyMuPDF, LangChain)	Requires external libraries (e.g., Haystack, LangChain)	No direct integration; external tools needed	Can be integrated via LangChain or Haystack
Interface	CLI + API	REST API	GUI + CLI	API + CLI
Scalability	Low (designed for local use)	High (designed for production servers)	Not scalable	Moderate (can support multiple users)

2.4. Tool selection

We aim at selecting three different tools.

2.4.1. Category 1: Chatbot with Keyword Search

ChatGPT. Its conversational interface combined with powerful language understanding makes it ideal for keyword-based querying and exploratory interaction.

2.4.2. Category 2: PDF Reader with Integrated RAG System

ChatPDF. Its ability to ingest PDFs and answer questions through a retrieval-augmented generation system provides a seamless approach for document-based querying.

2.4.3. Category 3: Systematic Reviews Tools

These tools are specifically designed for structured data extraction in the context of systematic literature reviews. They emphasize standardization and accuracy in collecting data from scientific studies.

They support collaboration, integration with other research tools, and are optimized for extracting data from scientific articles using customizable templates and predefined guidelines.

- **[RobotReviewer](#) / [RobotSearch Overview and Impressions](#)**

RobotReviewer is an automated tool designed to extract and analyze data from clinical trial reports, especially those in PDF format. Its primary objective is to simplify and accelerate the systematic literature review process, specifically within the context of clinical trials.

RobotSearch, on the other hand, is a complementary tool used to perform automated searches for clinical trials in databases, aiming to identify the most relevant studies for a given topic. While RobotReviewer focuses on data extraction from existing trials, RobotSearch facilitates the identification of pertinent clinical

trials, which often serves as a preliminary step before applying tools like RobotReviewer.

Impressions:

This was the tool we attempted to install (and ultimately succeeded) on a virtual machine. The main issue is that it is primarily designed to be deployed on more powerful servers. We struggled to enable GPU utilization—requiring a complex installation process on a virtual machine—and the tool ran extremely slowly. It is clearly not intended for standard users without significant technical expertise or dedicated hardware.

- **Excluded Tools: Paid Options or Insufficient for Our Needs**

Covidence

Covidence is a platform designed to facilitate the conduct of systematic literature reviews, particularly in health and social sciences. It is used for the management, screening, and data extraction of articles in systematic reviews, assisting researchers in organizing and analyzing large volumes of information.

Covidence offers a limited free trial, allowing users to upload up to 500 records (articles or bibliographic references) to test the platform before subscribing.

However, Covidence does not perform automatic extraction of complex data from articles using advanced artificial intelligence techniques such as natural language processing or retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). Instead, it provides tools that support and expedite manual data extraction for systematic reviews.

Due to its subscription model and lack of advanced automatic extraction capabilities, Covidence was excluded from our evaluation.

Comparative table: Covidence, Rayyan y EPPI-Reviewer

Feature	Covidence	Rayyan	EPPI-Reviewer
Primary Use	Management and screening of systematic reviews	Collaborative screening of systematic reviews with AI	Complete systematic review with advanced tools
Automation	Basic rules and data autocomplete	AI-assisted inclusion/exclusion suggestions	AI, text mining, and advanced NLP
Data Extraction	Structured forms with manual autocomplete	No data extraction functionality	Full support for structured

			extraction and analysis
AI/NLP Usage	No AI for selection or extraction	AI used for screening (not extraction)	AI/NLP used for screening and content analysis
Collaboration	Teamwork with conflict resolution	Teamwork with smart tagging and filtering	Teamwork with advanced control tools
Interface	Intuitive and easy to use	Simple and fast	Comprehensive but more complex
Export Formats	Excel, RevMan	Excel, RIS	CSV, XML, SPSS, Stata, RevMan
Cost	Subscription (free trial with 500 records)	Free (basic version), Premium available	Paid (credit-based)

Rayyan

Rayyan does not offer specific data extraction functionality like Covidence or EPPI-Reviewer. It focuses on study screening using AI but does not allow for structured data extraction directly from papers.

◆ Capabilities

- ✓ Filters relevant studies using AI assistance.
- ✓ Allows custom tagging of selected studies.
- ✓ Supports team collaboration to decide on inclusion/exclusion.

▼ Limitations

- ✗ Does not provide data extraction forms.
- ✗ Does not automatically analyze or summarize studies.
- ✗ Does not enable extraction of tables or metrics from articles.

EPPI-Reviewer

EPPI-Reviewer is significantly more advanced than Rayyan in terms of data extraction. It is a comprehensive tool for systematic reviews, with full support for data extraction and analysis.

◆ Capabilities

- ✓ Create customized data extraction forms with multiple fields (e.g., population, intervention, outcomes).
- ✓ Apply text mining and NLP techniques to automatically analyze documents.
- ✓ Visualize extracted data through charts and tables within the platform.
- ✓ Export information in formats such as CSV, XML, SPSS, Stata, or RevMan.

▼ Limitations

- ✗ It is not as intuitive as Covidence or Rayyan.
- ✗ Requires more manual setup to configure extraction forms.

Offers a 1-month free trial.

Data Extraction

SysRev

SysRev primarily focuses on streamlining efforts and efficiently organizing and structuring data. However, it does not specialize in the automatic extraction of data from documents, unlike tools such as RobotReviewer.

DistillerSR

DistillerSR is a software platform specifically designed to facilitate systematic literature reviews in scientific research. It is primarily used to organize and manage the review process, from study selection through data extraction to results synthesis.

This tool is targeted at research teams conducting systematic reviews, especially in fields such as medicine, social sciences, and other disciplines where handling large volumes of studies and data is critical. DistillerSR is recognized for its ability to enhance the efficiency, quality, and transparency of the review process.

DistillerSR offers automation capabilities for parts of the data extraction process, including the creation of customizable templates that guide reviewers in extracting key information from studies. These templates can be tailored to the specific needs of the review, such as PICO characteristics (Population, Intervention, Comparator, Outcomes).

The platform also facilitates the assessment of study quality and risk of bias. It can integrate with risk-of-bias assessment tools, helping to ensure the integrity of the systematic review results.

DistillerSR uses algorithms to automate parts of the data extraction process directly from studies. For instance, the platform can identify and extract structured data from articles, such as trial outcomes, interventions used, effect measures, and other quantifiable metrics.

Although automated extraction does not fully replace human involvement, DistillerSR significantly reduces reviewer workload by identifying and pre-

populating portions of extraction forms with data that is clearly available in the studies—such as numbers, percentages, and other numerical values.

While DistillerSR provides automation features that accelerate and support the data extraction process, it is not entirely autonomous. Automated extraction is limited to information that is easily identifiable and standardized across studies, such as numerical values, standard outcomes, or structured metadata. For more complex or unstructured data, manual input from reviewers is still required.

Note: No free trial is available. The platform is priced at approximately \$20 per user.

2.4.4. Category 4: Research Assistant Tool

[Google Notebook LM](#)

Google NotebookLM is an online research and note-taking assistant developed by Google Labs. It leverages artificial intelligence—specifically the Gemini model—to help users interact with their own documents. NotebookLM can generate summaries, explanations, and answers based on uploaded content. One of its standout features is "Audio Overview," which presents documents in a conversational podcast-like format.

Originally launched in 2023 under the name Project Tailwind, NotebookLM allows users to upload a wide variety of file types, including PDFs, Google Docs, websites, and Google Slides. Once the materials are uploaded, the tool analyzes them and establishes meaningful connections between topics, thanks to Gemini's multimodal understanding capabilities.

In September 2024, Google introduced the "Audio Overview" feature, which enables users to convert complex documents into engaging audio summaries with a single click. This innovation has been recognized for its potential to make dense academic content more accessible and digestible.

Google emphasizes privacy in NotebookLM. User data—such as uploaded sources, queries, and generated responses—is not used to train the underlying AI model. This commitment to data confidentiality is central to the platform's appeal in academic and enterprise settings.

Initially targeted at researchers, NotebookLM has also gained traction among businesses and students. In December 2024, Google launched NotebookLM Plus, a premium version aimed at enterprises and paid Gemini subscribers.

Conclusions

After this analysis, we have decided to use for our experiment: **ChatGPT, ChatPDF and Google NotebookLM.**

Given that the experiments were conducted between April 30 and May 14, 2025, the versions of the tools accessed were: the *GPT-4o* model on ChatGPT; *Gemini 2.5 Flash* on NotebookLM; the *Fast* mode in ChatPDF, which uses dynamic routing between *GPT-4o* and *GPT-4o-mini*, making it impossible to identify the exact model in each session.